

GROUP PARACHORS BY GIBLING'S METHOD. PART II.

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Group parachors for the groups C—CH₂—OH (69.7); C—C≡N (66.7); C—N≡C (59.1) have been determined. It is observed that even group parachors are not constant in the same homologous series. Introduction of a ring or a branch chain or increase in length of the carbon chain lowers the group parachor. For isomerides the effect of length of the straight chain is more marked than of the branch chain or a ring.

In previous papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 115, 222; 1948, 28, 175) structural parachors for certain groups by Gibling's method have been evaluated. The work is extended in this paper to other groups.

Group Parachor for C—CH₂—OH

TABLE I

Compound	P _{obs.}	E. C.	Groups subtracted.	P for (C)—CH ₂ —OH
<i>n</i> -Ethyl alcohol CH ₃ —CH ₂ .OH	127.5 127.3 126.8 126.6 Mean 127.0	0.1	CH ₃ —(C)	71.7
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol CH ₂ =CH.CH ₂ .OH	152.7 153.8 Mean 153.2	0.2	CH ₂ = (C), (C)=CH.(C)	69.0
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol CH ₃ —CH ₂ .CH ₂ .OH	165.4 165.8 164.7 Mean 165.4	0.2	CH ₃ —(C) and (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	70.2
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₂ .CH ₂ .OH	202.9 203.4 Mean 203.2	0.4	CH ₃ —(C) and 2(C)—CH ₂ .(C)	68.0
<i>iso</i> -Butyl alcohol 	202.1	0.4	2CH ₃ —(C) and (C) > CH.(C)	69.1
<i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₃ —CH ₂ .OH	243.3	0.6	CH ₃ —(C) and 3((C)—CH ₂ —(C)	68.1
<i>iso</i> -Amyl alcohol 	241.4	0.6	2CH ₃ .(C) and (C) > CH.(C)	68.4

TABLE I (contd.)

Compound.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	E. C.	Groups subtracted.	$P_{\text{for C-CH}_2\text{-OH.}}$
<i>ter.</i> Amyl alcohol $\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array} \begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagup \\ \text{C} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{CH}_2\text{-OH} \end{array}$	241.1	0.6	3CH ₃ -(C) and $\begin{array}{c} (\text{C}) \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ (\text{C}) \end{array} \begin{array}{c} (\text{C}) \\ \diagup \\ \text{C} \\ \diagdown \\ (\text{C}) \end{array}$	72.5
Benzyl alcohol $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-CH}_2\text{-OH}$	259.6	0.7	5(C)-CH=(C) and $\begin{array}{c} (\text{C}) \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C}-(\text{C}) \\ \\ (\text{C}) \end{array}$	70.7
<i>n</i> -Hexyl alcohol $\text{CH}_3\text{-(CH}_2)_4\text{-CH}_2\text{-OH}$	276.2	0.7	CH ₃ -(C) and 4(C)-CH ₂ -(C)	61.1
<i>n</i> -Heptyl alcohol $\text{CH}_3\text{-(CH}_2)_5\text{-CH}_2\text{-OH}$	313.4	0.9	CH ₃ -(C) and 5(C)-CH ₂ -(C)	58.3
<i>n</i> -Octyl alcohol $\text{CH}_3\text{-(CH}_2)_6\text{-CH}_2\text{-OH}$	354.4	1.2	CH ₃ -(C) and 6(C)-CH ₂ -(C)	59.2

Mean 66.7

In taking mean for the parachor of (C)-CH₂-OH group, the last three values, which show very great deviation, are omitted. The following table illustrates that the structural parachors for groups reproduce experimental results better than Sugden's values. The values substituted in the last three compounds obviously show a great deviation from the observed values, but even then they approach experimental values more than Sugden's values.

TABLE II

Compound.	P (Structural).	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	P (Sugden).
Ethyl alcohol	125	127.5, 127.3 126.8, 126.6	132.2
Allyl alcohol	153.9	152.7, 153.8 165.4, 165.8	160.2
<i>n</i> Propyl alcohol	164.9	165.4, 165.8 and 164.7	171.2
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	204.9	202.9, 203.4	210.2
<i>iso</i> Butyl alcohol	202.7	202.1	210.2
<i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol	244.9	243.3	249.2
<i>iso</i> Amyl alcohol	242.6	241.4	249.2
<i>ter.</i> Amyl alcohol	238.3	241.1	249.2
Benzyl alcohol	258.6	259.6	266.1
<i>n</i> -Hexyl alcohol	267.6	276.2	288.2
<i>n</i> -Heptyl alcohol	302	313.4	327.2
<i>n</i> -Octyl alcohol	343.9	354.4	366.2

Group Parachor for C—CN or C—C≡N

TABLE III

Compound.	Obs.	R. C.	Groups subtracted.	P for (C)—CN.
Propionitrile CH ₃ —CH ₂ .CN	160.5	0.2	CH ₃ —(C), (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	65.3
<i>n</i> -Butyronitrile CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₂ .CN	210.2	0.4	CH ₃ —(C) and 2(C)—CH ₂ —(C)	66.0
<i>iso</i> Valeronitrile $\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{CH} \\ \diagup \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array} \text{—CH—CH}_2\text{.CN}$	237.4	0.5	2CH ₃ —(C), (C) $\begin{array}{l} \diagup \\ \text{CH} \\ \diagdown \end{array} \text{—(C)}$ and (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	64.5
Benzonitrile C ₆ H ₅ —CN	255.5	0.7	5(C)—CH=(C) and $\begin{array}{l} \text{(C)} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ \text{(C)} \end{array} \text{= (C)}$	66.6
Phenylacetonitrile C ₆ H ₅ —CH ₂ .CN	293.6 293.4	0.9	5(C)—CH=(C), (C)—CH ₂ —(C) $\begin{array}{l} \text{(C)} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ \text{(C)} \end{array} \text{= (C)}$	64.6
<i>o</i> -Toluenitrile CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .CN	292.5 292.9	0.9	4(C)—CH (C) (C) $\begin{array}{l} \text{(C)} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ \text{(C)} \end{array} \text{= (C)}$ and (C)—CH ₃	65.3
	290.6 Mean 292.0			
<i>n</i> -Valeronitrile CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₃ .CN	236.6 237.4 Mean 237.0	0.5	CH ₃ —(C) and 3(C)—CH ₂ —(C)	61.9
<i>n</i> -Capronitrile CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₄ .CN	276.6	0.7	CH ₃ —(C) and 4(C)—CH ₂ —(C)	61.5
<i>iso</i> Butylacetonitrile (CH ₃) ₂ :CH—CH ₂ —CH ₂ .CN	275.0	0.7	2CH ₃ —(C), (C) $\begin{array}{l} \diagup \\ \text{CH} \\ \diagdown \end{array} \text{—(C)}$ and 2(C)—CH ₂ —(C)	62.5
<i>n</i> -Heptonitrile CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₅ .CN	316.1	0.9	CH ₃ —(C) and 5(C)—CH ₂ —(C)	61.0
<i>n</i> -Nononitrile CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₇ .CN	395.2	1.5	CH ₃ —(C) and 7(C)—CH ₂ —(C)	59.9
<i>n</i> -Octylic nitrile CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₆ .CN	356.0	1.2	CH ₃ —(C) and 6(C)—CH ₂ —(C)	60.8
<i>m</i> -Toluenitrile CH ₃ —C ₆ H ₅ .CN	295.6	0.8	4(C)—CH=(C), (C)—CH ₂ $\begin{array}{l} \text{(C)} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ \text{(C)} \end{array} \text{= (C)}$	69.0
<i>p</i> -Toluenitrile CH ₃ —C ₆ H ₅ .CN	295.2 295.9 294.4 Mean 295.2	0.8	"	68.6
				Mean 66.7

Lower members of the series alone are considered on taking mean, as higher members give very low values.

In the following table the values obtained by Sugden's method and by our method are compared with the observed values. The values obtained by introducing group parachors show better agreement with the experimental results in the case of lower members of the homologous series which were considered in taking mean.

TABLE IV

Compound.	P (Structural).	P _{obs.}	P (Sugden).
Propionitrile	161.9	160.5	159.0
<i>n</i> -Butyronitrile	201.9	201.2	198.0
<i>iso</i> -Valeronitrile	239.6	237.4	237.0
Benzonitrile	255.6	255.5	253.9
Phenylacetonitrile	294.7	293.6, 293.4	292.9
<i>o</i> -Tolunitrile	293.4	292.5, 292.9, 290.6	292.9
<i>n</i> -Valeronitrile	241.8	236.6, 237.4	237.0
<i>n</i> -Capronitrile	281.8	276.6	276
<i>iso</i> -Butylacetonitrile	279.2	275.5	276
<i>n</i> -Heptonitrile	321.8	316.9	315
<i>n</i> -Nononitrile	402	395.2	393
<i>n</i> -Octylic nitrile	361.9	356.0	354
<i>m</i> -Tolunitrile	293.7	295.6	292.9
<i>p</i> -Tolunitrile	293.3	295.2, 295.9 294.4	292.9

TABLE V

Compound.	P _{obs.}	E. C.	Groups subtracted.	P for $\begin{matrix} (C) \\ (C) \end{matrix} > (C)-(C)$
Anisole $C_6H_5-O-CH_3$	265.6	0.7	5(C)-CH=(C) and (C)-O-(C)	71.9
<i>o</i> -Nitroanisole	322.1	0.9	4(C)-CH=(C), (C)-C NO ₂ =(C) and (C)-O-(C)	72.9
<i>p</i> -Nitroanisole	322.6	0.9	"	73.4
				Mean 72.7

The parachors obtained by structural and Sugden's method are compared with the experimental values.

TABLE VI

Compound.	P (Structural).	P _{obs.}	P (Sugden).
Anisole	266.4	265.6	266.1
<i>o</i> -Nitroanisole	321.9	322.1	324.7
<i>p</i> -Nitroanisole	321.9	322.6	324.7

Group Parachor for C—CONH₂

TABLE VII

Compound.	<i>P</i> _{obs.}	<i>E. C.</i>	Group subtracted.	<i>P</i> for (C).CH ₂ —OH.
Acetamide CH ₃ .CONH ₂	148.0	0.2	CH ₃ —(C)	92.6
Propionamide CH ₃ —CH ₂ .CONH ₂	181.2	0.3	CH ₂ —(C), (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	85.9
Benzamide C ₆ H ₅ —CONH ₂	279.9	0.7	5(C)—CH=(C), (C) (C) } C=(C)	91.0
Salicylamide C ₆ H ₄ (OH).CONH ₂	295.3	0.8	4(C)—CH=(C), (C) (C) } C=(C)	94.63
Phenylacetamide C ₆ H ₅ —CH ₂ .CONH ₂	320.2	1.0	5(C)—CH=(C), (C)—CH ₂ —(C) and (C) } C=(C) (C)	91.2
				Mean 91.07

The structural parachor values and those obtained from Sugden's method are compared with the observed values in the following table.

TABLE VIII

Compound.	<i>P</i> (Structural).	<i>P</i> _{obs.}	<i>P</i> (Sugden)
Acetamide	146.07	148.0	150.8
Propionamide	186.37	181.2	189.8
Benzamide	279.97	279.9	284.7
Salicylamide	291.74	295.3	304.7
Phenylacetamide	320.07	320.2	323.7

Group Parachor for C—CH₂—NO₂ or C—CH₂—N

TABLE IX

Compound.	<i>P</i> _{obs.}	<i>E. C.</i>	Groups subtracted.	<i>P</i> for (C)—CH ₂ —NO ₂ .
Nitroethane CH ₃ —CH ₂ .NO ₂	171.2	0.25	CH ₃ —(C)	115.75

Parachor calculated by structural method is 171.2 and those calculated by Sugden's method is 170.8. The work needs further confirmation.

Group Parachor for C—CH₂—O—NO
(Nitrite group)

TABLE X

Compound.	<i>P</i> _{obs.}	<i>E. C.</i>	Groups subtracted.	<i>P</i> (C)—CH ₂ —O—NO.
<i>n</i> -Butyl nitrite CH ₃ —(CH ₂) ₃ —CH ₂ .O.NO	251.8	0.6	CH ₃ —(C), 2(C)—CH ₂ —(C)	116.4
<i>iso</i> Amyl nitrite (CH ₂) ₃ : CH—CH ₂ .CH ₂ .O.NO	287.4	0.75	2CH ₃ —(C), (C) (C) } CH—(C)	114.25
			and (C)—CH ₂ —(C)	Mean 115.32

The structural parachor values and those obtained from Sugden's method are compared with the observed values in the following table.

TABLE XI

Compound.	P (Structural).	P _{obs.}	P (Sugden).
<i>n</i> -Butyl nitrite	250.72	251.8	248.8
<i>iso</i> Amyl nitrite	288.47	287.4	287.8

TABLE XII

Compound.	P _{obs.}	E. C.	Groups subtracted.	P
Phenyl isocyanide $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NC}$	255.2	0.6	5(C) = CH-(C)	83.1
<i>o</i> -Tolylisocyanide $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NC}$	292.9	0.8	4(C) = CH-(C), (C) C = (C) and CH_3 -(C)	83.0
<i>p</i> -Tolyl isocyanide	295.5	0.8	CH_3 -(C), 4(C) = CH = (C)	85.4
Mean	295.0 295.3		(C) C = (C)	
<i>o</i> -Anisyl isocyanide $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NC}$	314.1	0.9	(C) = O-(C), 4(C) = CH = (C), (C) = C-O	81.8
<i>p</i> -Anisyl isocyanide	314.5 315.0	0.9	(C) C = O	82.2
				Mean 83.1

The values obtained by structural and Sugden's methods are compared with the observed values in the following table.

TABLE XIII

Compound.	P (Structural)	P _{obs.}	P (Sugden).
Phenyl isocyanide	255.2	255.2	230.5
<i>o</i> -Tolyl isocyanide	293.0	292.9	269.5
<i>p</i> -Tolyl isocyanide	293.0	295.5, 295.0	269.5
<i>o</i> -Anisyl isocyanide	315.4	314.1	289.5
<i>p</i> -Anisyl isocyanide	315.4	314.5, 315.0	289.5

Structural values are in close agreement with the observed values. The evaluation of group parachors again reveals that the values are not constant even for the same homologous series, but fall as we ascend the series. The increase in the length of the carbon chain lowers the parachor value of the group. For isomeric compounds the lowering caused by the branch chain is less than the straight chain. The same is true if a ring is introduced instead of a branch chain.